

ESiWACE3 Newsletter

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News

HPCW 3.0 Released: Open-Source Benchmarking Suite for Climate and Weather Simulations

The High-Performance Climate and Weather (HPCW) benchmarking suite has officially gone open-source with the release of version 3.0.

HPCW is designed to make it easier to benchmark new supercomputing systems, focusing on applications related to weather and climate research. The suite automates much of the complex setup required to build and run large-scale scientific models, helping users test performance with minimal manual intervention.

For over 30 years, the global Top500 list has ranked supercomputers using the LINPACK benchmark – a test of pure mathematical performance. However, as today's systems and applications become more diverse, a single benchmark no longer tells the whole story. Complementing benchmarks like Green500 (energy efficiency) and Graph500 (data-intensive workloads), HPCW brings a new domain-specific approach, assessing performance on realistic weather and climate workloads.

The HPCW suite includes both full models and model components, such as:

- ICON – the German weather and climate model framework
- NEMO – the Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean
- ecTrans – a key numerical library used by ECMWF and Météo-France

Version 3.0 introduces support for the Japanese NICAM model (Nonhydrostatic Icosahedral Atmospheric Model), aligning with the goals of the HANAMI project. HPCW now includes the open-source dynamical core of NICAM and infrastructure for an idealised test case.

HPCW currently runs on major European and Japanese HPC systems – including DKRZ/Levante, ECMWF/HPC2020, R-CCS/Fugaku, and BSC/MareNostrum5 – and the developers welcome contributions and extensions to new platforms.

Explore HPCW on GitLab: <https://gitlab.dkrz.de/hpcw/hpcw>

Documentation: <https://hpcw.gitlab-pages.dkrz.de/hpcw/>

HPCW v3.0

Open Source Release

<https://gitlab.dkrz.de/hpcw/hpcw>

HPCW

*High-Performance Climate and
Weather Benchmarking Suite*

Why it matters?

- Automated benchmarking of weather & climate codes
- Open-source and community-driven
- Easy deployment on supported platforms

HPCW contains both full models and model subcomponents

ICON

MICAMDC

IFS ecTrans
ecRad
dwarf-p-cloudsc

NEMO

Supported Platforms

Levante (DKRZ)
HPC2020 (ECMWF)
Fugaku (R-CCS)
MareNostrum5 (BSC)

Save the Date: 9th ENES HPC Workshop

The 3rd phase of the Centre of Excellence (CoE) in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe, ESiWACE3, presents the 9th ENES HPC Workshop!

This edition will take place at the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) offices in Norrköping, Sweden, from Tuesday 19 to Thursday 21 May 2026 (lunchtime to lunchtime), allowing for four half-day sessions.

The themes of the 9th workshop will build on those of the 2024 edition, with an increased emphasis on collaboration across projects and initiatives. Further details about the programme, speakers, registration, and deadlines will be shared in the coming months.

But for now – SAVE THE DATE!

The poster is split into two vertical panels. The left panel shows a photograph of a yellow building on a canal in Norrköping, Sweden, with the text 'Coming soon' written in a large, black, cursive font. The right panel has a light blue background with a vertical green line on the left. It features the text 'Save the Date' in orange, '9th ENES HPC WORKSHOP' in dark blue, and '19- 21 May 2026' and 'SMHI Norrköping (Sweden)' in dark blue. At the bottom, it includes the esiwace logo and the SMHI logo. On the right edge, there are logos for EuroHPC and the European Union.

ESiWACE3 at EuroHPC Users Day 2025 in Copenhagen

ESiWACE3 took part in the EuroHPC Users Day, held on 30 September – 1 October 2025 in Copenhagen, joining Europe's high-performance computing community to exchange experiences, share results, and present new tools and opportunities.

At the ESIWACE3 booth, courtesy by EuroHPC, the project showcased its latest developments to support the weather and climate modelling community, including:

- The new HPCW3.0 benchmark, designed to assess and optimize the performance of weather and climate models on current and emerging HPC architectures.
- The Open Call for Services, which offers support for domain-specific tools and technologies to help scientists prepare their codes for the exascale era.

Joachim Biercamp from DKRZ and Maria Arista from BSC-CNS represented ESIWACE3 at the event, engaging with participants and sharing insights on how the Centre of Excellence is contributing to Europe's weather and climate simulation capabilities through supercomputing.

Reflecting on the event, Maria Arista highlighted the value of this exchange:

“Engaging with users and HPC experts was an amazing burst of energy, since we are working hard to strengthen this community in climate and weather – especially as we focus on our last year and a half of the project.”

Participation in EuroHPC Users Day provided an excellent opportunity to connect with the EuroHPC community, strengthen collaborations, and promote ESIWACE3's mission to advance Earth system modelling and HPC innovation across Europe.

ESiWACE3 Launches Its New Website

We are pleased to announce the launch of the new ESIWACE3 website, now available at esiwace.eu!

The redesigned website offers a clearer structure and a more engaging experience, making it easier to explore how ESIWACE3 supports scientists and developers on the path to exascale computing..

The redesigned website is more user-friendly, making it easier for visitors to navigate and helping the dissemination of the Centre of Excellence's work across the European weather and climate community.

Visitors can now discover:

- Better organized information about ESIWACE3's mission, goals, and impact
- Detailed pages on each Work Package and their activities
- Comprehensive overviews of the services offered to the community
- Project videos, now properly displayed and easier to access
- A new calendar featuring upcoming events and training opportunities
- A dedicated section with training materials to support learning and collaboration

This new online presence reflects ESIWACE3's commitment to transparency, collaboration, and innovation in advancing weather and climate simulation in Europe.

👉 Visit the new website at www.esiwace.eu to explore all the updates and resources.

Updates

Milestones:

Milestone 3.5 Application of the FDO standard developed in D3.3 to example climate-simulation datasets using an automated approach: This milestone demonstrates the application of the FAIR Digital Object (FDO) standard, as examined in Deliverable D3.5, to example climate-simulation datasets. Building upon the strategic framework established in Milestone M3.1, we now validate the FDO concept by applying it to real-world datasets through a machine-actionable, automated approach. The implementation focuses on adopting FAIR principles by leveraging Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), Data Type Registries (DTR), and automated cataloging standards such as Spatio Temporal Asset Catalogs (STAC).

Read D3.5 [here](#).

News from the neighbours

Upcoming conferences and events

- [HiPEAC26](#): 26-28 January 2026, Krakov, Poland
- [EGU26](#): 3-8 May 2026, Vienna, Austria
- [ISC26](#): 22-26 June 2026, Hamburg, Germany

Training events

Find collected information on upcoming and past training events from all consortium partners and projects we are involved with [here](#).